

Intuitionistic Fuzzy Subalgebras (Ideals) with Thresholds (λ, μ) of BCI-algebras

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Abstract : Based on the theory of intuitionistic fuzzy sets, the concepts of intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebras with thresholds (λ, μ) and intuitionistic fuzzy ideals with thresholds (λ, μ) of BCI-algebras are introduced and some properties of them are discussed.

Keywords : BCI-algebra, intuitionistic fuzzy set, intuitionistic fuzzy subalgebra with thresholds (λ, μ) , intuitionistic fuzzy ideal with thresholds (λ, μ) .

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